

Prevalence and Clustering of Risk Factors of Noncommunicable Diseases among Industrial Workers of a Public Sector Undertaking

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Abstract:

Introduction: The four main types of NCDs are cardiovascular diseases, cancers, chronic respiratory diseases, and diabetes which account for over 80% of all NCD deaths before age 70. Even though it is understood that NCD risk factors are commonly shared, a single risk factor could contribute to several NCDs, and conversely, a single NCD could be the outcome of multiple risk factors. Therefore, understanding the simultaneous presence of risk factors can guide coordinated health system strategies.

Aim: This study was conducted with the objective of estimating the prevalence and clustering of risk factors of common NCDs among industrial workers of Upper Assam

Materials and Methods: A community based cross-sectional study was done among permanent employees of a public sector undertaking with an estimated sample size of 330. The study tool was adapted from WHO STEPS wise approach which was used to estimate the prevalence of risk factors.

Results: 244 (76.7%) of the study participants were in the 45–59-year age group and 287 (90.3%) were males. Current tobacco use was found in 62.3% of study participants. Harmful use of alcohol was observed in 5.7% of study participants. 98.4% study participants consumed <5 servings of fruits and vegetables. Low physical activity was found in 24.2% of study participants. Overweight and obesity was observed in 51.6% and 12.3% of study participants respectively. Hypertension and raised fasting blood glucose was found in 48.4% and 31.1% study participants respectively. Raised total cholesterol and raised triglycerides was found in 18.6% and 56.9% of study participants respectively. Overall clustering was found in 272 (85.5%) of study participants.

Conclusion: The prevalence of most of the behavioural and biochemical risk factors and clustering in the study population was high as compared to studies on different population subgroups across the country. The baseline information on the prevalence of risk factors provided by this study can help this population and their health policymakers in devising proper strategies to reduce the impact of NCDs on the population.

Keywords: NCD Risk Factors, WHO STEPS Approach, Clustering, NCDs.

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Introduction

Noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) are responsible for 74 million deaths globally each year. The four main types of NCDs are cardiovascular diseases, cancers, chronic respiratory diseases and diabetes which account for over 80% of all NCD deaths before age 70. [1] In India approximately 66% of all deaths are caused by NCDs. [2]

The majority of NCDs stem from four modifiable behaviours: tobacco use, harmful use of alcohol, unhealthy diet and physical inactivity. These four behaviours lead to four significant metabolic/physiological alterations: raised blood pressure, overweight/obesity, raised blood glucose

and raised cholesterol levels. [3] At the core of NCD prevention is the recognition and control of most prevalent risk factors. Today's risk factors are NCDs of tomorrow. [4] It is widely recognised that NCDs are complex diseases influenced by multiple factors, often working in combinations to accelerate the onset of these conditions. [5] Even though it is understood that NCD risk factors are commonly shared, a single risk factor could contribute to several NCDs, and conversely, a single NCD could be the outcome of multiple risk factors. Therefore, understanding the simultaneous presence of risk factors can guide coordinated health system strategies. [6]

Workers within any organization constitute a significant demographic. Their well-being, awareness of health and willingness to adopt healthy habits are anticipated to impact their efficiency, prevent the occurrence of NCDs, decrease healthcare expenses, and consequently enhance the financial condition of the workplace. [7] A significant number of risk factors and illness related to NCDs have been documented among industrial workers in India. [8] Prevalence of risk factors and the NCDs themselves can cause losses in productivity which is important to the industries. As there is a sparsity of studies on the prevalence of NCD risk factors among the industrial population in India, particularly in North-East India, this present study was done to estimate the prevalence and clustering of risk factors of common NCDs among industrial workers of Upper Assam.

Materials and Methods

A community based cross-sectional study was conducted among industrial workers of a Public Sector Undertaking (PSU) in upper Assam from 2017-2019.

Study setting: There are seven major PSUs in Upper Assam. [9] For operational feasibility one PSU was randomly selected for the purpose of the study. The selected PSU was an integrated oil and gas conglomerate that is involved in various aspects of energy industry that includes refining, transport, marketing etc. of petroleum and gas.

A list of all the employees was obtained from the Human Resource Department of the selected PSU. All permanent employees aged ≥ 18 years and <60 years with employment duration of ≥ 1 year were included in the study. Contractual employees, pregnant females and persons with debilitating illness were excluded.

The required number of employees was selected randomly from this list using a random number table. Selected employees were contacted telephonically and/or personally. Three attempts were made to contact each of the selected employees. They were explained the purpose of the study and the process involved in the study. The employees who consented to participate in the study were then called to the Occupational Health Centre on a given date and time for the interview, anthropometry, and sample collection.

Sample size: For sample size calculation, p was taken as 0.50 (50%) (as similar studies on industrial population in India were only a few), absolute precision 0.07 (7%) and $z=1.96$ for 95% confidence interval, which yielded a sample size of 196. Considering a design effect of 1.5 and a non-response rate of 10%, the final sample size was 327, which was rounded off to 330.

Data collection: Data was collected by interview method. After completion of the interview the participants were clinically examined for anthropometric parameters, heart rate and blood pressure. Then they were advised to come with overnight fasting on the next morning. Blood samples for fasting blood glucose and lipid profile were then collected in the morning of next day. Blood samples were analysed in the laboratory of the PSU.

Study instrument: The STEPS questionnaire (version 3.1) was used with local adaptations. Translation to Assamese and back translation into English and verification was done before using the translated version. Step 1 of the questionnaire included socio demographic and behavioural information for tobacco and alcohol use, physical activity and diet and dietary salt. Step 2 included Physical measurements, in addition to blood pressure measurements and Body Mass Index calculation (height, weight), waist circumference. Equipment used were calibrated every day before start of the measurements. Step 3 included Biochemical tests fasting blood glucose, total cholesterol, and triglycerides. Urinary sodium estimation was not done.

Ethical considerations: The Institute Ethical Committee of Assam Medical College and Hospital approved the study protocol vide No. AMC/EC/PG/12443 dated 14/09/2018. Informed and written consent was taken from all participants. Permission was also taken from the General Manager of selected PSU for conducting the study.

Definitions and cut offs used in the study: For risk factor prevalence estimation, the cut off values and definitions used were as per recommendation in STEPS.

1. **Tobacco use:** Currently using any form of tobacco, smoking and/or smokeless (daily and non-daily) in last 30 days of interview. [10]
2. **Harmful use of alcohol or heavy episodic drinking:** Consumption of ≥ 60 gm of pure alcohol for men and ≥ 40 gm of pure alcohol for women on an average day in the past 30 days. [11]
3. Consumption of less than five servings of fruits and vegetables per day was considered **insufficient fruit and vegetable intake** in the study participants. [10]
4. **Physical inactivity:** Physical activity information was collected using GPAQ format (as part of STEPS tool) and information was asked in three domains i.e. work, transport and leisure. Total of physical activity was further classified into low (less than 600 MET minutes per week), moderate (600–1500 MET minutes per week) and high (more than 1500 MET minutes per week). [11]

5. **Overweight** was defined as BMI between 25–29.9 kg /m² and **obesity** as BMI \geq 30 kg/m². [10]
6. **Abdominal obesity**: Abdominal obesity was defined as a waist circumference of \geq 90 cm in men and \geq 80 cm in women. [10]
7. **Raised Blood Pressure/Hypertension** was defined as having an average of systolic blood pressure \geq 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure \geq 90 mmHg, and/or self-reported current anti-hypertensive treatment for hypertension. [10]
8. **Raised fasting blood glucose/Diabetes**: Fasting capillary blood glucose of \geq 110 mg /dl or on medications for high blood sugar were considered to have diabetes mellitus. [11]
9. **Raised serum cholesterol and hypertriglyceridemia**:
 - A raised serum cholesterol level was defined as total cholesterol \geq 190 mg/dl. [12]

- Hypertriglyceridemia: Triglyceride level \geq 150mg/dl was considered as raised. [11]
10. Coexistence of any three or more (\geq 3) NCD behavioral or biological risk factors in the same individual was defined as **clustering of NCD risk factors** for this study. [12]

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed using Epi Info version 7.2.4.0. Quantitative data was summarised using mean and standard deviation. Qualitative data was expressed in proportion/percentages. Chi-square test was done to test association. P value $<$ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 318 employees participated in the study out of 330 that were contacted. Non-response rate was 3.6%.

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile of the study participants

Socio-demographic variables		Frequency (n=318)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	18-29	31	9.8
	30-44	43	13.5
	45-59	244	76.7
Sex	Male	287	90.3
	Female	31	9.7
Education	Up to Class 10	135	42.5
	Class 12 or Post High School Diploma	44	13.8
	Graduation and PG	139	43.7
Religion	Hinduism	288	90.6
	Islam	19	6.0
	Others	11	3.5
Caste	General	172	54.1
	OBC	96	30.2
	SC and ST	50	15.7
Marital Status	Never Married	27	8.5
	Currently Married	282	88.7
	Separated Widowed	9	2.8
Socio-economic status	Class 1 Rs 6574 and above	318	100.0
	Others Rs 6573 and below	0	0.0

244 (76.7%) of the study participants were in the 45–59-year age group and 287 (90.3%) were males.

Table 2: Prevalence of Risk factors of NCDs in the study population

Sl. No	Risk Factor	Frequency (n=318)	Percentage (%)
1.	Tobacco use	198	62.3
2.	Heavy episodic drinking	18	5.7
3.	Insufficient fruits and vegetables	313	98.4
4.	Insufficient physical activity/Physical inactivity	77	24.2
5.	Overweight	164	51.6
6.	Obesity	39	12.3
7.	Abdominal obesity	203	63.8
8.	Raised BP/HTN	154	48.4
9.	Raised fasting blood glucose/Diabetes	99	31.1
10.	Raised total cholesterol/Hypercholesterolemia	59	18.6
11.	Raised triglycerides/Hypertriglyceridemia	181	56.9

62 (19.5%) of the study participants were current smokers while 24 (7.5%) study participants were current daily smokers. 183 (57.5%) of the study participants were current smokeless tobacco users while 118 (37.1%) used smokeless tobacco products daily. 151 (47.5%) of the study participants abstained from alcohol in last 12 months while 80 (25.2%) were lifetime abstainers. 90 (28.3%) of the study participants were current alcohol users and 11 (3.5%) used alcohol daily. In a typical week fruits and vegetables were consumed on 2.99 and 6.89 days respectively.

The mean number of servings of fruit consumed on average per day was 0.5 while mean number of servings of vegetables consumed on average per

day was 2.33. 46 (14.5%) of the study participants added extra salt always or often to their food before eating or while eating. 132 (41.5%) of the study participants always or often ate processed foods high in salt.

The mean BMI was found to be 26.33 ± 3.34 kg/m² among the study participants. The mean waist circumference was 91.95 ± 7.77 cm among the study participants. Mean SBP and mean DBP were 135.17 ± 17.42 mmHg and 82.89 ± 9.48 mmHg respectively. The mean fasting blood glucose was found to be 110.59 ± 38.47 mg/dl. The mean total blood cholesterol was found to be 161.32 ± 39.62 mg/dl. The mean blood triglycerides were 152.16 ± 75.43 mg/dl.

Figure 1: Clustering of NCD risk factors in the study population

Figure 2: Distribution of study population according to number of risk factors present in an individual (n=318)

Overall, clustering of NCD risk factors was observed in 272 (85.5%) study participants. The median number of risk factors was four (4).

Table 3: Factors associated with clustering of risk factors in study population

Socio-demographic variable		Clustering				P value
		Yes	%	No	%	
Age (years)	18-29	25	80.6	6	19.4	0.50
	30-44	35	81.4	8	18.6	
	45-59	212	86.9	32	13.1	
Sex	Male	248	86.4	39	13.6	0.18
	Female	24	77.4	7	22.6	
Education	Up to Class 10	120	88.9	15	11.1	0.17
	Class 12 or Post High School Diploma	39	88.6	5	11.4	
	Graduation and PG	113	81.3	26	18.7	
Religion	Hinduism	244	84.7	44	15.3	0.43
	Islam	18	94.7	1	5.3	
	Others	10	90.9	1	9.1	
Caste	General	145	84.3	27	15.7	0.60
	OBC	85	88.5	11	11.5	
	SC and ST	42	84.0	8	16.0	
Marital Status	Never Married	18	66.7	9	33.3	0.01*
	Currently Married	247	87.6	35	12.4	
	Separated/Divorced/ Widowed	7	77.8	2	22.2	

Among the socio-demographic factors marital status of the study participants was found to be significantly associated with clustering of NCD risk factors ($p=0.01$)

Discussion

This study was done to estimate the prevalence of risk factors of common NCDs using STEPS methodology and their clustering in an industrial population of Upper Assam. The results indicate high prevalence of behavioural and biological risk factors of common NCDs in the study population. Also, clustering of risk factors was high in this population. Insufficient consumption of fruits and vegetables was the most prevalent behavioural risk factor, followed by tobacco use. Almost one in two individuals was overweight and had raised blood pressure. Nearly one in every three individuals had raised fasting blood sugar.

In this study, 62.3% study participants were using tobacco in any form (smoking or smokeless). The findings of tobacco use (both in smoked and/or smokeless forms) was higher when compared to Global Adult Tobacco Survey-2 India (1) (28.6%) and Assam (2) (48.2%) and other studies. (3–6) The results related to current smoking among the study participants were higher than what has been reported in other studies. [2–5]. The prevalence of tobacco use found in this study is higher than what was found by Suvetha et al. [13] and Kishore et al. [14] in industrial populations from different parts of the country. The prevalence of current alcohol use was higher than what was reported in similar studies by Mathur et al. [10] and Thakur et al. [11].

However, harmful use of alcohol in study participants was similar to what was found by Thakur et al. [11] Pelzom et al. found a higher prevalence of high alcohol consumption but their definition of high alcohol use was different than what was used in this study. [12] Kishore et al. in a study among factory workers in Delhi found adequate fruits and vegetables intake in none of the study participants. [14] The prevalence of <5 servings of fruits and/or vegetables consumption per day in this study was similar to the findings reported in other studies [5,11,15,16]. The prevalence of low/insufficient physical activity in this study is higher than what was reported by and Aryal et al. [16] while lower than the findings reported in other such studies on different population groups. [5,10–12].

Rengma et al. reported the overall prevalence of overweight (BMI 23.00–24.99 kg/m²) and obesity (BMI \geq 25.00 kg/m²) to be 32.6% and 10.8% respectively. [17] The prevalence for both overweight and obesity is lower than what was found in this study however different cut off were used to define overweight and obesity. The prevalence was higher when compared to other such studies. [5,10,12] The prevalence of raised BP/hypertension in this study was similar to what was reported by Mahanta et al. [18] in this region. A higher prevalence was observed when compared to studies from different parts of the country in general population and subgroups. [5,10–12] Prevalence of raised fasting blood glucose/diabetes in this study is higher than what has been reported by similar such studies. [10–12] Bora et al. found

raised total cholesterol and raised triglycerides among 24.5% and 11.5% study participants respectively. [19] Thakur et al. reported raised total cholesterol and raised triglycerides in 16.1% and 21.6% study participants respectively. [11] The prevalence of raised total cholesterol and raised triglycerides in the present study was higher than what was reported in the above-mentioned studies.

Clustering of risk factors in the current study was very high as compared to 40.2% found in National Noncommunicable disease monitoring survey in India [10] However, in the said survey only six risk factors have been considered. Zaman et al. have reported presence of 3 or more risk factors in 37% of study population. [5] Sarveswaran G has reported presence of ≥ 3 risk factors in 56.3% of study population. [20] Both Zaman et al. and Sarveswaran G have found clustering to be associated with age, male gender, education, which was not found in this study. None of these studies have reported the effect of marital status on clustering. Ahmed et al. have reported clustering in >70% of their study population. [21]

Limitations

There were some limitations in the current study. 76.7% of study participants in this study belonged to 44-59 years age group. Therefore, the results may not be generalized to all adults. That may also be one of the reasons of high prevalence of risk factors and clustering in this population. The number of women in the sample was comparatively less but in accordance with the company profile. [22] However, the results may not be generalized to all women. All the participants in this study belonged to SES Class 1, so the effects of socio-economic status on clustering could not be studied. Urine tests recommended in STEP 3 could not be done due to limited funds. Also, all the limitations of a cross-sectional study apply to the present study.

Conclusion and recommendations

From the findings of this study, it is concluded that prevalence of most of the behavioural and biochemical risk factors and clustering in the study population was high as compared to studies on different population subgroups across the country. The baseline information on the prevalence of risk factors provided by this study can help this population and their health policymakers in devising proper strategies to reduce the impact of NCDs on the population and measure the impact of these interventions. Health promotion by means of Health education on risk factors of NCDs will help to reduce the NCD burden. The health education messages should emphasize on the more prevalent behavioural factors in this population, which were, insufficient intake of five servings of fruits and/or vegetables, and tobacco and alcohol consumption

as found in this study. Periodic screening for these risk factors should be conducted. Authorities should provide necessary interventions to reduce the risk factors in individuals detected with risk factors tailored to local customs. These interventions should target more than one risk factor, keeping in mind the clustering of risk factors, which will also allow efficient use of resources.

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